

A Context-Aware Approach to Measurement Modeling and Inter-Model Consistency Preservation

Supplementary Information about Metamodels

Complete Constructs and Mappings

This document provides the supplementary construct definitions for the three proposed metamodels and the detailed metamodel instantiation for the vehicle braking system case study. It accompanies the main paper.

1 Complete Construct Definitions

1.1 Observation Metamodel Constructs

Table 1: Complete Constructs for Observation Metamodel. Underlined constructs are novel compared to SMM.

EClass	Definition	Attribute
Observation	Recorded finding	Identifier, Name, Time, Duration, Nature
Observation Source	Generates observation	SourceType, Identifier, Location, Protocol
Observer	Performs observation	Type, Identifier, Role, Accuracy
Observation Artifact	Output artifact	Identifier, Type, Time, Impact
Observation Interface	Exchange mechanism	InterfaceType, Inputs, Outputs
Observation Consequence	Effects of observation	Severity, Impact, Stakeholders
Observation Repository	Storage	Identifier, Type, Capacity
Observation Context	Context reference	Type, Location, State
Observed Phenomenon	Observed entity	Identifier, Type
Evidence	Supporting data	Category, Certainty
Observation Analysis	Analysis mechanism	Technique, Confidence

Table 1: Constructs for Observation Metamodel (continued)

EClass	Definition	Attribute
Observation Certainty	Certainty level	Precision, Reliability
Observation Granularity	Detail level	Temporal, Spatial
Observation Data	Measurement data	Unit, Value
Observation Evaluation	Evaluation	Criteria, Status
Observation Goal	Purpose	Type, SuccessCriteria
Observation Process	Process	StartTime, EndTime
Observation Relationship	Relations	Source, Target
Response Mechanism	Response	Type, Priority
Feedback Mechanism	Feedback	Source, Target

1.2 Phenomenon Metamodel Constructs

Table 2. Complete Constructs for Phenomenon Metamodel

EClass	Definition	Attribute
Phenomenon	Observed entity	Identifier, Type, Time
Phenomenon LifeCycle	Stage	Identifier, Stage
PhenomenonContext	Occurrence context	Identifier, Factors
PhenomenonElement	Properties	Identifier, Type
DetectionSource	Source	Identifier, Type
SpatialOccurrence	Location	Point, Size
TemporalOccurrence	Time	Timestamp, Duration
Phenomenon Relationship	Relations	Source, Target

Table 3. Complete Constructs for Context Metamodel

EClass	Definition	Attribute
Context	Observation context	Identifier, Type, Time
ContextConstraint	Constraints	Identifier
ContextScope	Scope	Spatial, Temporal
ContextScale	Scale	Type, Unit
ContextElement	Unit of context	Identifier, Value
ContextReasoning	Processing	Type, Reliability
ContextRelationship	Relations	Source, Target
ContextSource	Source	Identifier, Type
FormulaRelation	Formula	Quantities
Context		
SituationalFactor	Situation factors	Values

1.3 Context Metamodel Constructs

2 Detailed Metamodel Instantiation for the Vehicle Braking System

2.1 Mapping to the Phenomenon Metamodel

Table 4. Mapping to Phenomenon Metamodel

Target Concept	Source Element	Description
Phenomenon	BrakingDisk	Physical entity, high significance
PhenomenonElement	Disk attributes	size, material, temperature
Phenomenon	Interface	Friction interaction process
SpatialOccurrence	–	Brake location
TemporalOccurrence	–	Timestamp, duration

2.2 Mapping to the Observation Metamodel

Table 5: Mapping to Observation Metamodel

Target Concept	Source Element	Description
Observation	FrictionSystem	Friction measurement run
ObservationData	Attributes	friction, speed, pressure
Observation		
Source	Sensor	CAN-based measurement
Observer	–	Automated system

Target Concept	Source Element	Description
Observation		
Certainty	–	High reliability
Observation		
Process	–	Continuous sampling
ObservationGoal	–	Validation of friction range
Evidence	–	Sensor logs

2.3 Mapping to the Context Metamodel

Table 6. Mapping to Context Metamodel

Target Concept	Source Element	Description
Context	–	Emergency braking context
ContextElement	ActuationSystem	torque, trigger
ContextScope	–	Spatial + temporal scope
Context		
SituationalFactor	–	wet, 120 km/h, emergency
ContextConstraint	–	deceleration threshold
ContextReasoning	–	rule-based classification